

**Prevalence and risk factors of livestock diseases in Quetta District, Balochistan:
A participatory epidemiology study**

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ABSTRACT

Livestock diseases poses a major threat to animal productivity, farmer livelihoods, and public health in Pakistan. This study assessed the prevalence of livestock disease and identified associated risk factors in Quetta District, Balochistan, using participatory epidemiology methods. Data were collected from 50 livestock farms through structured questionnaire, field observations, and interviews, results revealed that foot and mouth disease (9.66%), theileriosis (8.33%), haemorrhagic septicaemia (6.4%), gastrointestinal parasites (6.88%), and avian influenza (6.64%) were the most common diseases. Disease prevalence was higher in female animals (51.1%) compared to males (48.8%). Seasonal variations were evident, with the highest burden reported in winter (32.95%). Major risk factors included lack of vaccination is (30%), poor housing (30%), limited veterinary access (14%), and overcrowding (12%). The findings highlight significant gaps in animal health management, with only 40% of farmers maintaining records and 14% participating in educational programs. Strengthening vaccination programs, veterinary infrastructure, farmer training, and adopting a One health approach are recommended to reduce disease burden and improve livestock productivity in the region.

INTRODUCTION

Livestock is central to Pakistan's economy, contributing 12% to GDP and over 56% to value of addition in agriculture (Amir Shahzad, 2022). In Balochistan, livestock accounts for 33% of provincial GDP and sustains nearly 70% rural households (Yaqoob & khosa, 2022). Despite its importance, the sector is constrained by high disease burden, poor management practices, and weak veterinary infrastructure. Common livestock diseases, such as foot and mouth disease (FMD), haemorrhagic septicaemia (HS), Peste des petits ruminants (PPR), contagious caprine pleuropneumonia (CCPP), anthrax and brucellosis, remains endemic and cause substantial economic losses and public health concerns (Farooq *et al.*, 2007; Ali *et al.*, 2017). Quetta District is the centre of livestock activity in Balochistan, is particularly vulnerable due to its semi-arid climate, scattered settlements, and limited vaccination coverage. Previous reports highlighted the urgent need for systemic epidemiological studies in the area. However, there is limited recent data on disease prevalence and associated risk factors. (Baseer Achakzai & Abbas Shah, 2017). This study aimed to assess the prevalence of livestock diseases and identity management and environmental risk factors in Quetta District using Participatory epidemiology methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The research was conducted in Quetta District, Balochistan (30.2°N, 67°E). The district experiences a semi-arid climate with hot summer and cold winters.

STUDY DESIGN AND SAMPLING

A cross-sectional survey was conducted over six months. Multistage sampling was used to select 50 livestock farms representing diverse ecological zones.

DATA COLLECTION

Data were obtained through structured questionnaire (27 items), from farm observations, and interviews. Information covered farmer demographics, animal species, disease prevalence, risk factors and farm management practices. Questionnaires were translated into Balochi, Pashto and Bravi. All close questions, and their answers are coded as "1" if the respondent said yes or no and "0" if they did not answer. Open questions were examined and categorized based on their answers.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The obtained data was saved in Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and analyzed with PAST software (version 4). Chi-square applied to test association between variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Farmer Demographics

Demographic profile of livestock owners and the characteristics of their animals is given in Table 1. A total of 50 livestock farms from Quetta District were included in this study with 50 respondents. All 50 farmers in the study were men. In terms of age, most farmers were between 20-25 years (24%)

and 35-40 years (24%), while the smallest group was those aged 26-30 years (14%). This shows that most farmers were young to middle-aged. In education sector, a large number of farmers were illiterate (40%), and the same percentage had only primary education (40%). Only 10% had secondary education, and 10% had veterinary training. This means that lack of education and technical training is a major issue in this area. In terms of farming experience, 40% had been farming for 5-10 years, and another 40% had more than 10 years of experience. Only 20% were farmers with less than 5 years of experience. Among the total 4500 animals from 50 livestock, 51.1% were female and 48.9% were male. This suggests that farmers keep more female animals, probably for milk and reproduction purposes. Regarding the numbers of workers, about 42% of farms had 5 or fewer workers, 34% had 6-15 workers, and only 24% had more than 15 workers.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of animals' farm owners/workers.

Variable	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Age of the respondent	20-25 years	12	24.00
	26-30 years	7	14.00
	31-35 years	11	22.00
	35-40	12	24.00
	Above 40 years	8	16.00
Educational Status	Primary	20	40.00
	Secondary	5	10.00
	Veterinary doctor	5	10.00
	Illiterate	20	40.00
Farm Ownership	Yes	30	60.00
	No	20	40.00
Farming Experience	< 5 Years	10	20.00
	5-10 Years	20	40.00
	> 10 Years	20	40.00
Gender of Animals	Male	2200	48.88
	Female	2300	51.11
Number of Workers in Farms	=<5	21	42.00
	6-15	17	34.00
	> 15	12	24.00

Animal population and Disease prevalence

50 livestock farms were surveyed with 4500 animals present in livestock, the largest group of animals were chickens (27.7%), followed by sheep (20.4%) and cows (18.2%). Cattle were the least common

(12.2%). Regarding health problems, the most common diseases reported were Foot and mouth diseases ($n=435$, 9.66%), Theileriosis ($n = 375$, 8.33% $p < 0.00106$), fowl cholera (7.97%) and gastrointestinal parasites (6.9%) are most prevalent disease among animals of livestock. Other important diseases included brucellosis (6.8%), avian influenza (6.6%), and haemorrhagic septicaemia (6.4%). Less common but still significant were mastitis (3.6%), lumpy skin disease (4.6%), and tick-borne infections (5.0%). About two-thirds of farmers (66%) reported observing typical disease symptoms in their animals, while one-third (34%) had not. When it came to treatment, only 36% of farmers said they used preventive treatments, while 64% did not. even fewer farmers (22%) reported taking preventive measures such as vaccination, isolation, or record-keeping. This shows a big gap in disease prevention practices.

Table 2. Animal population, livestock disease and health practices reported by farmers.

Questions	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Animals present in livestock	Sheep	916	20.35
	Goats	970	21.55
	Cow	817	18.15
	Cattle	549	12.2
	Chickens	1248	27.73
Health problems in animals of livestock's	Bovine tuberculosis	245	5.44
	PPR	246	5.46
	Anthrax	270	6.00
	Tick borne infections	227	5.04
	Brucellosis	305	6.77
	CCPP	249	5.53
	Avian Influenza	299	6.64
	Cholera	359	7.97
	Mastitis	160	3.55
	FMD	435	9.66
	Lumpy Skin	208	4.62
	Newcastle disease	280	6.22
	Gastrointestinal parasite	310	6.88
	CCHF	244	5.42
	Theileriosis	375	8.33

	Hemorrhagic Septicemia	288	6.4
Typical symptoms observed	Yes	33	66.00
	No	17	34.00
Treatment to prevent disease	Yes	18	36.00
	No	32	64.00
Preventive measure to maintain animal health	Yes	11	22.00
	No	39	78.00

Seasonal trends

The results of the present study indicated clear seasonal variations in livestock diseases. The highest prevalence was reported in winter (32.95%, n = 1483), with major disease including pneumonia, foot and mouth disease FMD, gastrointestinal infections, CCPP, CCHF, and bovine tuberculosis. Autumn was the second most affected season (29.17%, n = 1313). In summer (19.62%, n = 883), the dominant diseases were observed included haemorrhagic septicaemia, tick-borne infections, mastitis, and lumpy skin disease. Spring showed the lowest prevalence (18.24%, n = 821), mainly associated with PPR, brucellosis and anthrax. The findings suggested that livestock are at greater risk of disease outbreaks during the colder months.

Table 3. Seasonal distribution of livestock disease in Quetta District.

Season	common disease	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Summer	Hemorrhagic Septicemia, tick-borne disease, mastitis, lumpy skin	883	19.62%
Winter	Pneumonia, foot and mouth disease, gastrointestinal infections, CCPP, CCHF, bovine tuberculosis	1483	32.95%
Spring	PPR, brucellosis, anthrax.	821	18.24%
Autumn	Theileriosis, avian influenza, fowl cholera, Newcastle disease.	1313	29.17%
Total		4500	100%

Risk factors

The analysis of risk factor assessment associated with spread of disease on Quetta livestock. The factors which are contributing to the spread of disease are lack of vaccination and weather condition

(15, 30.00% 10, 20.00%, $p < 0.002$). majority of housing condition of farm is good (20, 40.00% $p < 0.03$). Is overcrowding being risk factor, mostly respondent says no (29, 58.00% $p > 0.10$).

Table 4. Risk factors contributing to the spread of livestock diseases.

Questions	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage	p-value
Risk factors contributing to the spread of disease	Lack of vaccination	15	30.00	0.002
	Poor sanitation and hygiene	5	10.00	
	Overcrowd in animal shelters	6	12.00	
	Limited access to veterinary services	7	14.00	
	Weather condition	10	20.00	
	Other reasons	7	14.00	
Housing conditions of farm and livestock	Excellent	5	10.00	0.03
	Good	20	40.00	
	Fair	10	20.00	
	Poor	15	30.00	
Is overcrowding being a risk factor for disease transmission	Yes	21	42.00	0.10
	No	29	58.00	

Management practices

The result of the study revealed that a majority of respondents (50%, $n = 26$, $p < 0.02$) were aware of the importance of quarantine and isolation for sick animals. Regarding hygiene practices, 50% of farmers considered them somewhat important, while 30% reported them as very important, and 20% as not important ($p > 0.06$). the major challenges in livestock and farm management include limited supplement availability 30%, poor sheltering 26%, lack of veterinary services 20%, disease outbreaks 14%, and insufficient knowledge 10%, showing a significant association ($p < 0.005$). veterinary care was sought only when problems occurred by 46% of farmers, 34% accessed care at least once a year, and 20% almost never ($p < 0.04$). awareness of common diseases was reported by 44% of respondents, while 56% were unaware ($p > 0.07$). furthermore, only 14% of farmers utilized educational resources such as workshops and training courses, whereas the majority 86% did not ($P > 0.39$).

Table 5. Farm management practices adopted by livestock farmers.

Questions	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage	p-value
Quarantine and isolation for sick animals	Yes	26	52.00	0.02
	No	24	48.00	
Importance of hygiene practice for livestock	Very important	15	30.00	0.06
	Somewhat important	25	50.00	
	Not important	10	20.00	
Challenges faced during livestock and farm management	Lack of veterinary services	10	20.00	0.005
	Limited supplement	15	30.00	
	Diseases outbreak	7	14.00	
	Poor sheltering	13	26.00	
	Insufficient knowledge	5	10.00	
Veterinary care for livestock and farms	At least one a year	17	34.00	0.04
	Only when there is problem	23	46.00	
	Almost never	10	20.00	
Aware of common disease	Yes	22	44.00	0.07
	No	28	56.00	
Utilization of educational resources (workshop, courses etc.)	Yes	7	14.00	0.39
	No	43	86.00	

DISCUSSION

The study confirms that livestock in Quetta District suffers from a high prevalence of infectious diseases, with FMD, HS, and theileriosis emerging as major threats (Ali *et al.*, 2017; Hasan *et al.*, 2023). Seasonal variation was clearly observed, with winter having the highest prevalence. This may be explained by cold stress, increased indoor confinement, and better survival of pathogens in lower temperatures. In contrast, summer showed fewer outbreaks, but more vector borne infections such as tick-borne diseases because of favorable weather.

It is noteworthy that only 22% of farmers take preventive measures against animal diseases. The major reasons for this include limited financial resources, lack of education among farmers, and weak veterinary facilities. To address this issue, it is necessary to improve awareness programs and facilitate access to veterinary services.

Although the disease burden was found to be higher in females, attributing this to reproductive stresses alone is only a guess as there are no supporting data on reproductive status. Future studies should collect detailed information on reproductive factors to test this hypothesis more robustly.

Risk factors such as poor vaccination coverage, weak veterinary services, and low farmer awareness explain the persistence of endemic diseases. The farmers are dependent on traditional remedies and absence of record-keeping for facing reflected challenges in further region of South Asia (Musa et al., 2014). Importantly, disease transmitted from animals to humans, such as anthrax, brucellosis and bird flu, make it clear that livestock care is linked to the health of human, animals and the environment.

In global terms, the situation in Quetta is similar to Nigeria, Bangladesh and other poor countries, where better care and supervision of animals is very important (Herrero et al., 2012; Dadar et., 2021).

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that livestock in Quetta district are suffering from a lot of infectious and parasitic diseases. The most prevalent disease among them are: FMD, HS, theileriosis, PPR and gastrointestinal worms. Female animals and small animals were more affected. Diseases breakout is high in winter and autumn. The major causes of diseases are: low vaccination rates, poor sanitation, overcrowding, and lack of veterinary facilities. These findings suggest that improving livestock health is essential to both preserve animal production and protect humans from zoonotic diseases.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research, the following recommendations are made:

1. Vaccines against FMD, HS and PPR should be prioritized and mobile vaccination teams should be formed for remote areas.
2. Veterinary centers and mobile clinics should be expanded so that animals can easily receive treatment.
3. Paramedical veterinary workers should be trained to help monitor and treat diseases.
4. Public awareness campaigns and training workshops should be conducted to help people recognize diseases, keep records, and follow protective measures.
5. New methods of disease surveillance should be incorporated into extension services to ensure farmer involvement.
6. Improved systems of animal enclosures, sanitation, and waste disposal should be promoted.
7. Sick animals should be isolated and quarantined to prevent the spread of diseases.

8. There should be strengthen cooperation between the veterinary, medical and environmental sectors to control diseases transmitted from animals to humans.
9. Close monitoring of health risks associated with milk, meat and poultry products should be maintained.
10. A database should be established at the provincial level for disease surveillance.

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